

Trailblazer in Teaching Education: BEED Graduates Competencies and Experiences in their Career Choices

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Abstract

Original Research Article

This study aims to trace the employment status, competencies, and career pathways of Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) graduates from Bulacan State University from 2019 to 2023. It examines and determines the relationship between graduates' competencies and the impact of these hard and soft skills on their current employment and professional growth. In this study, a mixed-methods research design was used; data were gathered through an online survey and semi-structured interviews with selected BEED graduates. Quantitative data were analyzed by the researchers using statistical analysis, whereas descriptive narrative analysis was employed for qualitative responses. The results revealed that most graduates were currently employed in education-related fields. It highlighted that graduates' competencies, both hard and soft skills are interrelated. The findings emphasize the importance of the acquired hard and soft skills, for their employment performance.

Keywords: BEED Graduates, Employment Status, Competencies, Career Pathways, Tracer Study.

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INTRODUCTION

In the constantly changing world of education, teachers mold student futures to be globally competent, achieve excellence, and contribute to the community. Graduates must possess the competencies needed for their careers. According to Sieck (2021), competence is the ability to do something well and effectively perform a task or job. Career choices among BEED graduates are influenced not only by their acquired competencies but also by their experiences, personal interests, and job market realities. This study determined the competencies and experiences of BEED graduates and how these factors influence their career decisions, aiming at the effectiveness of teacher education programs in the teaching profession. The research gap is the relationship between the Bachelor of Elementary Education graduates' soft and hard skills. The researchers investigated the relationship between the two variables to identify the skills that graduates use in their current jobs. This study focused on the employment trends, competencies, and career pathways of Bachelor of Elementary

Education (BEED) graduates from 2019 to 2023 and how their competencies relate. The research study analyzed the interlinkage between BEED graduates' competencies and experiences in their career choices.

According to a study by Palattao et al. (2018) cited in Gaytos et al. (2023), developing communication, problem-solving, research, and technology skills is crucial for education graduates in the Philippines to be globally competitive in the 21st century. However, according to Punla and Farro (2022), BEED graduates lack English communication competencies, including the art of questioning and technological skills. This research study explored the employment trends, competencies, and career pathways of Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) graduates from 2019 to 2023 and their experiences in career choices.

The significance of this study is that it contributes significantly to various educational stakeholders and encourages administrative support to enhance programs and curricula that directly respond to the employability and

preparedness of future graduates. It determined the soft and hard skills these graduates acquired during their academic training and how they influenced their career decisions and professional success. It recognizes the career paths of BEED graduates from the academic year 2019 to 2023, analyzing their employment trends and the relevance of their educational background to their current jobs.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

METHODOLOGY

Qualitative and quantitative methods were used to collect data on BEED graduates. This method allows for a comprehensive understanding of graduates' competencies and experiences. Both numerical and narrative data were used to facilitate a well-rounded analysis of the study's key variables.

Research design

This study utilized a mixed-methods approach, integrating quantitative and qualitative data to comprehensively understand the research problem. Mixed methods research (MMR) combines numerical data with in-depth qualitative insights in a single study or sustained inquiry program to generate a more complete understanding than is achievable with a single method (Fetters, 2020, as cited in Fabregues et al., 2023). Using a convergent parallel design, quantitative and qualitative data were combined through triangulation. The researchers used a correlation analysis to measure the strength and direction of the relationship between graduates' hard and soft skills. Additionally, descriptive narrative analysis categorized and interpreted qualitative responses from the interviews and open-ended questions. Researchers have used this method to understand personal experiences and perspectives through storytelling or narrating of the answers of BEED graduates.

Participants

The population of this study consisted of 112 participants who had a bachelor's degree from Bulacan State University. 87 were female and 25 were male. One hundred graduates fall within the age of 20-30, 10 are 31-40 and 2 are 40-50 ages. Participants were selected using Stratified Random Sampling was used to randomly select the participants from each year (2019, 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023) to ensure the equal representation of each year. The sample size collected using the Raosoft calculator was used to determine the number of graduates involved in the study at a 95% significance level from a population of 348 to 183 respondents.

However, only 112 graduates participated in the study due to response rate limitations. Despite not reaching the ideal sample size, the collected responses offer valuable insights into the career pathways of BEED graduates.

Instrument

In this study, a Likert-scale questionnaire and semi-

structured interviews were conducted. These instruments were used to collect the respondents' demographic profiles, graduates' competencies, and experiences in their current profession. The researchers provided one (1) set of questionnaires for a bachelor's degree in elementary education. Each questionnaire consisted of six (6) categorical scale questions, ten (10) Likert-scale questions, and three (3) open-ended questions. The questionnaire was adapted and modified from existing related studies, which were adapted from Salendab et al. (2023). The researchers utilized AI-assisted tools, such as ChatGPT, to generate sample questions aligned with the identified competencies. The research instrument used in this study was validated by three experts.

Procedure

The data-gathering procedure for this mixed-method research began with obtaining formal consent from the Dean of the College of Education to access the names of graduates from academic years 2019 to 2023. This step helped researchers identify respondents who were graduates and inform them of the study by sending a formal invitation letter.

After providing consent, the researchers used Google Forms as the survey form to collect data from graduates. In this form, the study included a consent letter outlining the data privacy of the study. Graduates were contacted through social media, such as Facebook, and participants answered the form using Google Mail. The researchers gathered data on graduates' demographic profiles and experiences in their career choices using structured surveys and semi-structured interviews. Graduates were asked about their employment trends, competencies acquired in their current jobs, and factors affecting their career choices.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results highlighted the employment trends, demographic profiles, competencies and experiences of graduates in their career choices.

The results of the study can be highlighted with the help of tables and interpretations given below.

1. Profile of BEED graduates of 2019-2023

The data presentation began with the profile of the graduate respondents. The table shows the distribution of age, sex, year of graduation, employment information, and highest educational qualifications. Each table includes the interpretation of the data and relevant related studies.

1. Age

The age distribution of BEED graduates from 2019 to 2023 illustrates the respondents' age groups and provides insights into their length of service in the teaching profession.

Table 2. Distribution of Graduates According to Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
20-30	100	89.29%
31-40	10	8.93%
41-50	2	1.79%
Above 50	0	0.00%
TOTAL	112	100.00%

Table 2 shows the distribution of BEED graduates by age. Most graduates fall within the age of 20-30. The data show that most respondents are young (Salendab & Sanchez, 2023). According to Almejas et al. (2017), as cited in Salendab et al. (2023), this result implies that BEED graduates are developing careers in the teaching profession. This was followed by graduates aged 31 to 40, and the lowest number of graduates, which was 2, belonged to 41 to 50. Age also affects graduates' experience. Additionally, according to Almutahar et al. (2015), as cited in Pratono (2021), junior teachers tend to have less

experience than senior teachers. However, senior teachers with a more qualified and balanced perspective are considered more mature and stable; therefore, they are not vulnerable to pressure at work.

2. Sex

The distribution of BEED graduates by sex represents the gender composition of the respondents. It helped to identify whether graduates were male or female, providing gender insight representation in teacher education.

Table 3. Distribution of Graduates According to Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Female	87	77.68%
Male	25	22.32%
TOTAL	112	100.00%

Table 3 shows the distribution of BEED graduates by sex. Most of the graduates were female, with a percentage of 77.68%. This was followed by male graduates (22.32%). There were 87 female graduates and 25 male graduates. The data showed that most BEED graduates were female. These figures suggest that females dominate the primary education teaching profession. According to Moreau (2018) and Watt et al. (2012), as cited in Ulanday (2021), the teaching profession includes a complex interplay of contextual and individual factors, with gender being one of the factors related to career choice. Gender differences in choosing to teach are reflected in the fact that men are much less attracted to enrolling in teacher education programs, and numerous studies focusing on the perception of the teaching profession have demonstrated that it is perceived as increasingly feminized. The second perspective is associated with traditional concepts of masculinity and femininity that

result in a gender division of occupations about which decisions are usually made during upbringing and schooling. According to Wigfield (2020), as cited in Pikic (2022), while men tend to be employed in professions related to engineering and technology, women find their place in professions dedicated to childcare, elderly care, and healthcare, with many professions considered exclusively female.

3. Year Graduated

The distribution of BEED graduates according to their graduation year aims to present the total number of graduates from the academic years 2019 to 2023. This table identifies enrollment trends and aids in selecting respondents for the data collection.

Table 4. *Distribution of Graduates According to Year of Graduation*

Year of Graduation	Frequency	Percentage
2019	25	22.32%
2020	10	8.93%
2021	27	24.11%
2022	27	24.11%
2023	23	20.54%
TOTAL	112	100.00%

Table 4 shows the distribution of graduates according to their year of graduation. The total number of graduates who answered was 112, whereas 2021 and 2022 answered the highest of the 27 participants. This was followed by 2019, which had 25 participants; there were 23 participants in 2023, and the least number of participants answered in 2020, with 10 participants. The number of BEED graduates in 2020 was lower than in other years; therefore, COVID-19 adversely affected education, including learning disruptions and decreased access to education (Onyema, 2020). Therefore, the pandemic has affected the following years, resulting in online learning using synchronous and asynchronous modalities. Graduates likely encountered similar challenges, such as employment due to the pandemic. According to Agbayani-

Pineda (2025), the transition to online learning significantly impacted the challenges and experiences of these graduates. Meanwhile, the year 2023 has consistent enrollees in the BEED program. Quipit et al. (2024) confirmed that enrollment in the BEED program has remained relatively stable over the years, indicating a consistent interest in this field.

1.4 Employment Information

The employment information of BEED graduates aims to determine their current job status and whether they have pursued further studies. It also seeks their career paths, whether in the teaching profession or other fields.

Table 5. *Distribution of Graduates According to Employment Information*

Employment Information	Frequency	Percentage
Elementary Teacher	63	56.25%
Teaching but not in Elementary	2	1.79%
Employed but not in Teaching	34	30.36%
Self- Employed	8	7.14%
Not Employed at All	5	4.46%
TOTAL	112	100.00%

Table 5 shows the distribution of teachers according to their employment information. Most graduates pursue careers as elementary school teachers. This was followed by thirty-four respondents who reported being employed but not in teaching. Their current job titles include technical assistants, quality and policy experts, assistant supervisors, administrative assistants, admin clerks, nanny/cleaning job workers, head supervisors, team leader/registrars, customer service representatives, transport delivery managers at Pepsi, gaming associate/inspectors, correction officers, admin assistants, encoders, associate III, sales associate, quote and design analyst, customer relations associate, consultant, collection specialist, and assistant. Next were graduates who pursued a teaching career but not as elementary teachers; they were currently working as instructors at a university. There are also

eight self-employed graduates whose occupations included CSR, managers, tutors, and bartenders. Lastly, the group with the lowest number of graduates, five was not employed at all. According to the findings, graduates acquired the values, attitudes, skills, and competencies necessary for their on-field jobs. Their college education taught them various knowledge and practical abilities, including communication, human relations, information technology, problem-solving, and critical thinking (Sanchez-Danay, 2023). The high percentage of employment may be associated with the high demand for public and private school-teachers in implementing K to 12 programs (Pardo et al., 2021). Pending licenses for some graduates has contributed to unemployment as it is a basic entry requirement for public institutions and some private sectors (Pentang et al. 2022).

1.5 Highest Educational Qualification

The table presents the distribution of Elementary Education (BEED) graduates according to their highest

educational qualifications. The categories include doctorate holders, currently continuing my master's degree, currently continuing my doctorate, and college graduates.

Table 6. Distribution of Graduates According to Highest Educational Qualification

Highest Educational Qualification	Frequency	Percentage
Bachelor's Degree	97	86.61%
Currently continuing with units in Master's Degree	14	12.50%
Master's Degree Graduates	1	0.89%
Currently continuing with units in Doctorate Degree	0	0.00%
Doctorate Degree	0	0.00%
TOTAL	112	100.00%

Table 6 shows the distribution of BEED graduates according to their highest educational qualification. It was observed that 97 out of 112 respondents answered that a bachelor's degree was their highest educational qualification. According to Amahido (2024), others do not enroll in postgraduate education because they experience challenges that may hinder their ability to continue their careers and enhance their professional development. One of the challenges of not pursuing post-graduation education is limited access to resources and opportunities. In addition, Aguelo (2024) shows that some graduates are still preparing for their LET exam, which leads them not to pursue their postgraduate study during that time. It was followed by 14 respondents currently enrolled in a unit of a master's degree program. Only one of the graduates

holds a master's degree. As a result, G3 is a Teacher I at Pagasa Elementary School in Caloocan City, and the graduate is in 3 to 4 years of teaching. According to the results, none of the graduates from 2019 to 2023 have pursued a doctorate. Only one has attained a higher level of education, and this individual is from the 2019 batch.

1.6 Award Received

The table presents the Bachelor of Elementary Education graduates as respondents according to their award received.

Table 7. Distribution of Graduates According to Award Received

Awards Received	Frequency	Percentage
Division meet coach	2	1.79%
Coordinatorship	3	2.68%
Good Leadership Award	4	3.57%
Licensure Examination for Teacher	2	1.79%
Quality Enforce Award (Quarterly)	2	1.79%
Best Awardee	2	1.79%
2024 C.Y Top Agent/Elite Award	1	0.89%
Teaching Development Programs Certificates	2	1.79%
Most Diligent Teacher	3	2.68%
Cum Laude	1	0.89%
Best in Demo Teaching	2	1.79%
N/A	88	78.57%
Total	112	100.00%

Table 7 shows the distribution of graduates according to ward. Most of the graduates received no awards, with a percentage of 78.57; lack of recognition, encouragement, and appreciation is a significant reason employees leave an organization (Rybnicek et al., 2019 & Utomo, 2018, as cited in Chung & Khandhadia, 2024). The data show that BEED graduates received awards before their employment and during their work, and the participants received awards that could be their edge in applying for their current jobs. According to Ryan (2020), awards play a crucial role in employee retention and serve to establish influential role models within organizations. One of those awards is the best in demo teaching, cum laude, licensure examination for teachers, and a good leadership award.

Meanwhile, respondents also received awards during their employment because of their outstanding performance, such as the awards for teaching the division meeting coach awards and certificates for teaching development programs. Diligent teachers and BEED graduates who chose different careers were also recognized for their outstanding performance. The BEED graduate, who works as a customer service representative in an agility company, received the 2024 C.Y Top Agent/Elite

Award, and the respondent who works in PwC AC Manila as an associate III graduate was recognized with the Quality Enforce Award (Quarterly). This shows that even though most of the teachers did not receive any awards, there were still BEED graduates who were excellent at their work, even before and after graduating or during their employment.

2. Competencies of BEED Graduates

The following table shows the competencies of Bachelor's elementary education graduates; the data presentation begins with hard skills. Furthermore, the following data presented the soft skills and correlation analysis between the soft and hard skills of graduates. Interpretation of the data and relevant studies accompanies each table.

1. Hard Skills

The following table presents the distribution of respondents according to their competencies in hard skills.

Table 11. Summary of Hard Skills

Indicators	Ave Rating	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Numeracy Skills	2.83	0.98	Highly Skilled	Advanced Proficiency
2. Information, Media, and Technology Skills	3.06	0.90	Highly Skilled	Advanced Proficiency
3. Research Skills	2.90	0.93	Highly Skilled	Advanced Proficiency
OVERALL	2.93	0.92	Highly Skilled	Advance Proficiency

Table 11 presents hard skills' total mean and standard deviation, showing relatively close values across all skill areas. Information, media, and technology skills emerged with the highest competency level of 3.06 (SD = 0.90), suggesting that graduates feel relatively confident in this domain. According to Lamri and Lubart (2023), the definition of hard skills may vary by profession, for example, coding for computer science graduates or visual design for those in creative fields, but all involve measurable technical abilities. Additionally, Lamri and Lubart describe hard skills as abilities that develop from

practice, training, and experience to perform a specific task to a certain standard. Graduates obtain hard skills through education and training (Maulana et al., 2024).

2.2 Soft Skills

The following table presents data distribution on respondents' soft skills, including communication, cooperation and collaboration, critical thinking, leadership, problem-solving, human relations, persuasion, and negotiation skills.

Table 19. Summary of Soft Skills

Indicators	Ave Rating	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Communication Skills	3.15	0.82	Agree	Good Level of Proficiency
2. Cooperation and Collaboration Skills	3.35	0.87	Agree	Good Level of Proficiency
3. Critical Thinking Skills	3.26	0.83	Agree	Good Level of Proficiency
4. Leadership Skills	3.21	0.84	Agree	Good Level of Proficiency

5. Problem Solving Skills	3.11	0.83	Agree	Good Level of Proficiency
6. Human Relation Skills	3.20	0.83	Agree	Good Level of Proficiency
7. Persuasion and Negotiation Skills	3.12	0.77	Agree	Good Level of Proficiency
OVERALL	3.20	0.82	Agree	Good Level of Proficiency

Table 19 shows the interpretation of graduates' mean and standard deviation scores for soft skills. Cooperation and Collaboration skills had the highest mean, 3.35 (SD= 0.87). The lowest mean score was 3.11 (SD= 0.83), and graduates agreed that they had acquired Problem-Solving Skills. The results indicate that the respondents possessed good proficiency in Soft Skills. These skills can be a factor influencing a company's hiring of BEED graduates. These results may help the graduates get the job they want; according to Malik and Mohan (2022), cooperation and collaboration are

fundamental for effective teamwork; this competency helps employees navigate their work environments effectively and contribute positively to their teams. Therefore, possessing employees' soft skills is an edge to their work and environment, just like good communication skills and the 21st-century skills in high demand in today's generation. Critical thinking and problem solving skills are also important. According to Mahmood and Hasan (2020), critical thinking and problem-solving capabilities are essential to address challenges and make informed decisions.

Table 20. Correlation Analysis between the Soft Skills and Hard Skills of Graduates

Variables Correlated	r	Description	Sig-value	Decision	Interpretation
Hard Skills and Soft Skills	0.7621	Moderate positive linear correlation	0.00001	Reject Ho	There is significant relationship between the BEED graduates hard skills and soft skills

Based on the data presented in Table 20, there was a correlation analysis between the soft and hard skills of BEED graduates. The computed correlation coefficient ($r = 0.7621$) indicated a moderate positive linear relationship between the two variables. Hard skills tended to improve when soft skills increased. A link exists between these two competencies. According to Samosir (2025), hard and soft skills are interdependent. Soft skills enhance the application of these hard skills in a professional setting; without strong soft skills, the effectiveness of hard skills may diminish. The significance value ($p = 0.00001$) was well below 0.05, indicating that the results were statistically significant. The coefficient for each factor was tested, and all independent variables had a p-value less than 0.05. Therefore, when the null hypothesis is rejected, the alternative hypothesis is accepted, confirming that a significant relationship exists between BEED graduates' hard and soft skills. According to Cabasis and Sanson-Lozano (2024), the result implies a linear relationship between hard and soft skills, meaning that their influence and connection are direct.

career (Siddiky & Akter, 2021). However, there are still many people who studying education because of the high job opportunities and availability in that field (Fitria, 2023). In this study the most important factors that influenced graduates were their personal interest, passion for teaching, influence by family and other people, career growth and job opportunities. These factors play a significant role in shaping the career choices of graduates.

Below is a sample of the response from 1 graduate.

**GR 65 - "My personal interests and career advancement opportunities influenced my choice of career. I chose to teach in a private school after graduation to fully develop my skills and gain ample teaching experience in case I want to move forward in my career."*

Most BEED graduates enter private schools to gain experience and to enhance their teaching skills. This aligns with Tindowen's (2019) study that private schools are the avenue and training grounds for teachers to gain experience before going to public schools that offer competitive salaries. Thus, both internal motivation and external opportunities play crucial roles in shaping the career trajectories of education graduates.

Qualitative Result of the study

BEED Teacher

The factors of BEED Teachers

Decision-making is crucial in every part of life because it shapes the future and affects others, including the family. One of the problems students face is choosing a suitable

The challenges of BEED Graduates

According to Zydziunaite et al., (2020), schools should develop the potential to support teachers to experience

less stress and increase their self-esteem. Teachers commonly face challenges, such as heavy workloads, classroom management, preparing teaching materials, managing learners' behavior, and addressing the needs of learners. The 2022 graduates shared their teaching experiences and emphasized the challenge of handling different students' behaviors and dealing with parents' concerns and expectations, which are some challenges that graduates face in their profession.

***GR 65 - "The primary challenges I encountered in teaching were handling different students' behaviors and dealing with parents' concerns and expectations. However, the advantages I experienced included having creative freedom and the opportunity to continuously develop my skills."**

This experience is similar to that of Castroverde and Acala (2021), in which teachers struggled to contact the parents of the learners due to inactive contact numbers and a lack of gadgets. The graduates also shared the advantages of the teaching career. These advantages can help graduates successfully shape their careers. Tournier et al., (2019) supported this view, stating that teachers thrive in their careers when they feel supported and valued. In supporting teachers, especially new teachers, the number of challenges in teaching will be reduced.

The influence of education and work experience to the career choice of BEED Graduates

According to Gati et al. (2019) as cited by Azhenov et al. (2023), career selection can be one of life's most challenging decisions. When considering the numerous career paths that they could potentially follow, people often feel overwhelmed by the information they need to absorb. Education and work experience influence graduates career choice. According to Boholano (2012), as cited by Abas (2020), one may obtain a recognized job after graduation through quality education and proper training. Education programs help students make instructional materials and are sufficiently knowledgeable to handle learners in the teaching field. In addition, Pardo and Relon (2023) stated that education and employment are interconnected in shaping the present and future of individuals.

Below is a sample of the response from 1 graduate.

***GR 65 - "Looking back, my education and work experience played a significant role in shaping my career choice. My academic background provided me with the foundational knowledge and teaching strategies necessary for the profession, while my work experience allowed me to apply those skills in real classroom settings."**

Teaching but not in BEED

A BEED graduate pursued teaching but not in BEED

Salary is one of the reasons a person changes their career. This is a factor in choosing a career that is better than the program has finished. Graduates choose to find jobs that sustain their needs, which has become a person's motivation to

change jobs. According to Herzberg's theory, extrinsic motivators include status, job security, salary, and fringe benefits. The graduate changed his career to that of an instructor at Bulacan State University. According to Colot (2024), this concentration is attributed to the availability of more job opportunities, better career growth prospects, and higher salaries in urban areas. According to Nugraha et al., (2023), salary and incentives are ways to foster enthusiasm that encourages individuals to act and work hard to achieve optimal results.

***G45 "Salary, because of my salary I can pursue my graduate studies"**

Pursuing graduate education offers a wide range of professional, personal and financial growth. G45 chose to be a better instructor than a BEED teacher because, alongside problems related to promotion practices, professionals pursuing graduate studies education for career growth also experience challenges and barriers regarding finances (Cruz, 2024).

Embracing the Adjustment: A Path to Professional Growth

Changing careers requires adjustment, particularly when adapting to a new environment. Even though the adjustment period can be stressful, it has positive aspects, such as personal and professional growth. According to Rossier et al. (2023), the study of career development should consider what resources prevent specific vulnerabilities and what resources promote overall thriving in working lives. While the adjustment period may involve stress, focusing on positive outcomes can ease this transition. Employees with strong career adaptability who also experience higher job satisfaction are more likely to perceive work challenges as manageable tasks rather than overwhelming stressors (Wong, 2023).

***G45 "Adjustment period, but advantages it helps me a lot in professional growth."**

Career adaptability leads to positive outcomes during career transition, such as professional growth. It is conceptualized as a set of psycho-social resources for coping with developmental vocational tasks, participating in working life, and adapting to changes in the labor market and working conditions (Kvasková et al. 2023).

The Turning Point of Graduate Career Growth

According to Sagun and De Vera (2025), the influence of education and work experience on graduates is that they can develop their skills and gain experience in the different events they encounter. Graduates who have developed relevant skills through coursework and practical experience are better positioned to adapt to various job roles. Sometimes these graduates do not get the work they are supposed to do. That is why it is important to have training for them to have the skills they need in case they will not teach elementary pupils; according to Patton and Parker (2025), the importance of structured support and training for BEED graduates

transitioning into teaching roles outside of elementary education is important. Therefore, many BEED graduates find success in non-elementary teaching roles, which may include positions in secondary education or specialized training. This study indicates that their skills are transferable across different educational levels and sectors (Rizqi et al., 2024).

**G45 "It will influence my career growth."*

Employed But Not in Teaching

The decision making of BEED graduates that leads to different path

Family is among the most significant factors influencing graduates to change their career path. Changing career paths due to the family's financial situation also plays a crucial role. Parents' financial capabilities can either limit or expand their available career options. (Charara et al., 2024).

**GR21 - "my family, for now it's really hard and so different from teaching. I choose to be a teacher but not into now"*

Most of these teachers do not pursue teaching even if they want to because of the financial satisfaction their current work can provide to their families. According to Balboa et al., (2023), seeking employment overseas is believed to lead to better financial stability for their families. Therefore, teachers are in demand in every task because they are flexible and can do everything. The effect of this decision can lead to losing job satisfaction because they may struggle to fully embrace their new role fully (Hogg et al., 2023).

BEED graduate turns into Overseas Filipino Workers

There are many options for work after graduation that can affect decision making in choosing the right path for graduates, and one of the possible reasons is salary (Chua, 2021). The teaching profession in the Philippines often comes with low pay, driving educators to seek employment in other countries. Moreover, the salaries in the Philippines are in (Gumarang, 2021). Private school teachers often receive lower salaries than public school teachers. Therefore, BEED teachers chose to work abroad because of higher salaries (Salibay & Umadhay, 2023), proving that teachers working abroad earn much more than their counterparts in the Philippines, making it an attractive option for those seeking financial stability and better living conditions.

**G21 - "A high salary but hard."*

The influence and experience of BEED

Before entering college, many things can influence the choice of course they will pursue, one of which is during high school. According to Hadiyati and Astuti (2023), high schools can motivate students to pursue BEED courses. Students who excel in subjects like English, Mathematics, and Science may feel more confident in teaching these subjects later. This study aligns with the idea that early educational experiences shape career choices.

**G21 - "It is so different, but I experienced it here in Turkey as a kindergarten English teacher just part-time."*

The experience can be good or bad and can contribute to the decision making of this graduate if they pursue what they want. According to Mombaers et al., (2023), a lack of support can discourage students and contribute to their decision not to enter the teaching profession. Sometimes, even if they do not achieve the exact goal they want, there is still a chance to experience teaching just like teaching in kindergarten, because being a BEED teacher can also qualify for teaching at the kindergarten level. According to Ancheta et al., (2023), teachers in the BEED programme reported having experienced teaching kindergartens.

Self-Employed

Building growth through self-work

Learning from multiple angles is an effective method for self-growth. As you expose yourself to various views, you understand the world better. In the work field, embracing different viewpoints nurtures empathy. According to Tenedero (2001), sense of self is a fundamental aspect of intrapersonal intelligence, as cited in Dela Fuente et al., (2021). Intrapersonal intelligence is a form of self-management. Individuals with this kind of genius are highly introspective and tend to have a sixth sense or belief in a higher order. They are generally quiet and deliberate, work well alone, manage personal growth, and search for identity. They have excellent control over their feelings and moods. They express themselves using symbols. As cited in Dhania et al., (2021), PGIs are shown when individuals actively seek personal growth experiences and intend to involve themselves in the development process (Le Cunff, 2019). According to Hult (2020), motivation is crucial for unemployed persons to be committed to job-seeking and skill development.

**GR41 - "For growth, I love to learn from different perspectives."*

Discovering different career options

Employability skills assist students in obtaining the skills required for getting and keeping a job, both in their studies and after graduation. These programs are more concerned with skills beyond academic knowledge; they assist students in acquiring personal qualities, core skills, positive attitudes, and sound work ethics. Studies in the USA have found that recent graduates are likely to focus on values, such as pursuing meaningful and enjoyable work. (Quinlan & Renninger, (2022). Ilyas et al., (2023) emphasized the importance of employability skills development programs during and after graduation to enhance the employability of graduates. They said that employability components, such as graduates' personal qualities, core skills, attitudes, and work ethics, influence their employability. Gallup (2019), as cited in Ajayi et al., (2023), reported that graduates who experienced a sense of purpose in their work were more likely to align their work with their

interests, values, and strengths, and participate in a program or class that helped them think about pursuing meaningful work.

***GR41 - "You learned about different types of work."**

Self-Growth of Self-employed BEED graduate

Personal growth is a continuous process that requires mindfulness and fulfillment. In the work environment, it is crucial to influence career growth and the one's ability to develop in a company. Individuals prioritize personal development, and more attributes such as self-knowledge, flexibility, and adaptability are offered. Robitschek et al. (2012), as cited by Joo et al. (2021), identified four components of personal growth, readiness for change, planfulness, resource use, and intentional behavior. Readiness for change refers to preparedness to undertake self-change. Self-awareness is important to our behavior, satisfaction, and performance (Carden et al. 2022) as cited by (London et al. 2023). According to Zhu et al. (2017), as cited by Beutell et al., (2019), individual factors that can affect both the personal growth and exit intentions of self-employed entrepreneurs include engagement, strain, and family.

***GR41 - "Personal growth"**

Not Employed at All

Practicality dreams among unemployed BEED Graduates

The practical dreams of BEED graduates are compromised by real-life challenges, such as limited job opportunities, financial struggles, and the responsibility to support their families. These factors were felt by BEED graduates. Job mismatch has become an issue, as many BEED graduates are forced to pursue employment unrelated to teaching. According to Kadir et al., (2020), there is a positive relationship between job mismatch and unemployment among graduates owing to job unavailability and the need for income. According to Suna et al., (2020), as cited in Khalid (2019), job creation does not keep pace with the existing supply of graduates, which compels graduates to accept a job unrelated to their field of study to reduce unemployment. In February 2023, as reported by GMA News, the Labor Force Survey revealed that approximately 2.47 million unemployed Filipinos.

***GR 29- "Practicality Dreams"**

Unemployment BEED graduates face many challenges

BEED graduates often face challenges accessing public schools. It is easy to get hired in private schools, but this often results in lower pay. Owing to the competitive nature of public school employment, many graduates experience long waiting periods before securing a teaching position. Public school teaching jobs offer better salaries, job security, and benefits, which is why many graduates prefer them. However, obtaining a position in a public school is very competitive because of the large number of applicants. It is common

knowledge that the longer a graduate waits to land a job, the more costly the lost opportunities. According to Garcia et al., (2024), unemployment has become a major issue, and the problems caused by unemployment are both social and economic. Lack of job opportunities or other factors result in a lack of income sources, affecting the economic status of society. The International Monetary Fund (2020) reported on the cost of joblessness. According to this report, unemployment imposes high costs on individuals, society, and the country. When prolonged, this can lead to skepticism. Eventually, the value of education and training is lost among unemployed individuals. Furthermore, Abella et al., (2024) found that college graduates typically spend three–six months of job hunting before securing employment. Factors brought on by the pandemic also posed challenges to new graduates when seeking employment.

***GR 29 - "It is very easy to land a job in private schools, yet the salary is very low compared to public schools. There is so much competition because there are so many education graduates."**

It's hard to find a job among unemployed BEED graduates

BEED Graduates often begin planning their career paths, and if they can teach, they pursue a teaching career. However, finding a job is challenging due to insufficient experience. Many enhance their teaching skills and knowledge, hoping to gain more expertise and improve their chances of finding employment. They continue to follow their passion for teaching, believe in themselves, and dream of securing a job. They leave the workforce, discouraged after long periods of unemployment, look for jobs, or by suboptimal available opportunities (Wangchuk, 2020). As cited by Aljumah (2023) frictional unemployment occurs when workers leave their old jobs but have not yet found a new job. In addition, since many graduates cannot successfully apply their knowledge and abilities, underemployment has become a major problem (Hasan & Alvi, 2022). Additionally, several identified causes of youth unemployment are limited job opportunities, limited education levels, reluctance to migrate to places with more job opportunities, poor communication skills, and lack of work experience (Alil & Rahim, 2020) cited by (Kaharudin et al. 2023).

GR 29 – "Although I am currently unemployed due to personal reasons, it is actually my plan to start my master's degree this year. I am currently applying for a teaching job in a public school, so if there is one thing that influenced me to continue in this profession that is because of my passion for teaching. I experienced teaching for at least 2 years, and I can say that it is such a fulfilment for me."

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study determined the employment trends, competencies, and career pathways of bachelor's (BEED) graduates from 2019 to 2023 through the application

of qualitative and quantitative methods and analysis of the resulting data.

These sections summarize the key findings of the study of BEED graduates, including age, sex, year of graduation, employment, highest educational qualifications, and awards received. Most BEED graduates were young when entering the workforce, and most graduates were female. Most graduates currently pursue careers in their teaching. Based on these findings, the hard and soft skills of BEED graduates are necessary for their employment performance. These BEED graduates obtained complex abilities through formal education and hands-on experience, whereas soft skills can be acquired through personal and problem-solving skills. Not all graduates pursuing their ideal profession continue to find value and fulfillment by applying their competencies in various fields: this adaptability and the lasting impact of their academic and professional journeys.

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